

FUEL CELLS AND HYDROGEN
JOINT UNDERTAKING

HyCARE

Hydrogen CArrier for Renewable Energy Storage

Deliverable 6.1

System Specification

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1. Scope of the document

This document aims at defining the main features of the site targeted to receive the demonstrator pilot developed and built during the collaborative project HyCARE (referred as “storage system” within this document). More specifically, main requirements and boundary conditions apply to the 50 kg hydrogen storage system developed in the frame of this project.

This document also presents the result of a very preliminary risk analysis that has been initiated in order to anticipate as much as possible the different safety issues that could possibly happen during the utilization of the developed system. Taking into account the very early stage of the project and accordingly to the current level of information, this work and the recommendation associated shall not be considered as exhaustive and will be deeply complemented during task 7.1.

2. Receiving site description

The storage system will be received, commissioned and tested within ENGIE CRIGEN Hydrogen Lab. The storage system is foreseen as a plug and play system disposed within an adapted ISO container installed in an outdoor area at ENGIE site. The storage system will be connected to:

- An inlet pipe supplying the storage system with the hydrogen delivered by an electrolyser
- An outlet pipe that supplies the hydrogen delivered from the storage system to a fuel cells
- An electric connection to supply the storage system with electricity
- Eventually an inlet pipe of cooling water could be considered (the feasibility will depend on the request)

These components and the boundary conditions associated are described below. All remaining utilities (process air, nitrogen...) should be included within the storage system.

Water electrolysis unit

The electrolysis system will provide hydrogen gas to the storage system at a purity level defined by the existing purification system with the electrolyzer. The main specifications of the hydrogen production unit are listed in Table 1 below. The production system should be efficient enough to avoid heavy electricity consumption and improve round-trip efficiency of the whole unit. The electrolyzer should deliver hydrogen of high quality, meeting the requirements of the H₂ quality standard ISO 14687.

TABLE 1– MAIN CHARACTERISTICS OF ELECTROLYSIS SYSTEM

System	Rated power [kW]	Nominal production [Nm ³ /h]	Efficiency [HHV]	Nominal Pressure [bar abs]	Purity
Electrolyzer	53	~10	~65%	25	99.998%
					H ₂ O<10 ppm (-60°C)
					N ₂ <5ppm
					O ₂ <5ppm

The electrolyser will be connected to the national electric grid and renewable electricity profile will be simulated by varying the production profile of the electrolyser. The goal of the simulation will be to identify possible integrations of the developed system into a renewable energy source. In particular, both

photovoltaic and wind energy sources will be considered. For the computer simulation, the power of the renewable source and the time distribution along the day and the year will be considered.

Fuel Cell unit

It is projected to acquire 2 to 3 Fuel Cell units in the upcoming period. These systems will operate similarly and their combined power should comply with the specifications of the production and storage units. Fuel cells require a relatively high level of hydrogen quality which should follow the H₂ quality standard for hydrogen Fuel Cells ISO 14687.

Table 2 below shows some general characteristics of the Fuel Cell units:

TABLE 2– MAIN CHARACTERISTICS OF FUEL CELLS

System	Nominal System power [kW]	Nominal H ₂ flow [Nm ³ /h]	Efficiency [LHV]	Inlet Pressure [bar abs]	Purity
FC unit	4 kWe	3.0	~50%	1.5-1.8	99,95% H ₂ O ₂ <5ppm H ₂ O<5ppm
FC CHP (optional)	5 kWe (electrical) 10 kWth (thermal)	6.5	Up to 100%	1.3-2.0	99,999% recommended

The fuel cell unit will be in test and will supply electricity to an artificial load depending on the test need. The optional FC CHP system will include also an H₂ boiler which will be driven by the heat demand of the ENGIE building central heating and the electricity injected in the local grid. For computer simulation real loads will be considered, in order to simulate the integration of the energy storage system in real applications. Both residential and industrial applications will be considered. In particular, the power of the load and the time distribution along the day and the year will be taken into account.

Boundaries of hydrogen and heat storage

Details on each interface with H₂ storage (operating condition, inlet and outlet flows...) are schematically presented in figure 1.

Hydrogen at high purity level is fed into the storage unit at specified temperature and pressure. It is important to mention here that hydrogen pressure is strongly dependent on electrolysis system operating range (i.e. reducing hydrogen production rate from 100% to 10% might decrease outlet pressure to near atmospheric conditions). Of course, the addition of a buffer within the storage unit would help mitigate this issue. Hence, the storage unit should be adapted for occasional pressure drops potentially reaching near atmospheric pressure.

A nominal pressure of 25 bar for the H₂ produced by the electrolyser will be considered for testing. The running of the system with different pressures for the inlet hydrogen will be simulated, considering possible introduction of suitable buffer and compression systems.

The Fuel Cell unit is fed with desorbed hydrogen coming from storage system. The recovered hydrogen should be at mild pressure and temperature conditions to ensure a convenient operation of the Fuel Cell. Generally, hydrogen purity should not be affected by HyCARE storage and shall at least comply with ISO 14687-3 international standard for PEM Fuel Cell applications. It is important to mention here that the hydrogen flow needed for the fuel cell is strongly dependent on the fuel cells system operating range. Hence, the storage unit should be adapted for variation of outlet flow.

Available electric source on ENGIE site is provided in the figure 1 and should provide up to 64 Amp current. All remaining utilities (i.e. process air, nitrogen...) should be included within the storage system.

FIGURE 1—BOUNDARIES OF HYDROGEN & HEAT STORAGE SYSTEM

3. Regulatory boundaries and applying standard

Regulatory framework

The storage system must follow the following European regulations:

- 2014/68/EU Pressure Equipment Directive (PED) (formerly 97/23/EC) on the standards for the design and fabrication of pressure equipment
- 2014/34/EU directive on the harmonization of the laws of the Member States relating to apparatus and protective systems for use in potentially explosive atmospheres.
- 1999/92/EC Directive on minimum requirements for improving the safety and health protection of workers likely to be exposed to the risk of explosive atmospheres
- 2014/34/EU Directive related to equipment and protective systems intended for use in potentially explosive atmospheres

More generally, the storage system shall comply with all European regulation. Among others, the following directive should be considered for the transport operations:

- 2010/35/EU Directive 2010/35/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 June 2010 on transportable pressure equipment
- ADR 2017 European Agreement concerning the International Carriage of Dangerous Goods by Road

The metal hydride powder shall not be classified according to the CLP Regulation (EC) 1272/2008 regulation (no flammable solid, not water reactant, does not build flammable gases in contact with water).

Applying standards

The storage system should follow the recommendations of the following standards as guidelines. If it is not reasonable to follow one of these standards, the topic shall be discussed among the partners.

ISO 16111: 2018 (E) Transportable gas storage devices – hydrogen absorbed in reversible metal hydride

with a specific attention on the following sections :

- 5.2 Material selection,
- 5.2.3 Compatibility, volume dilation,
- 5.5 Overpressure and fire protection
- 6 Inspection and testing
- Annex A : Material compatibility for hydrogen service

This standard is considered as a good practice and will be discussed during the design.

EN 13445-3, Unfired Pressure vessels not subject to flame :

- part 3: Design.
- part 5: Inspection and testing.

EN 13480-5, Industrial metal piping

- part 5: Inspection and control.

ISO 15916/2015 Basic considerations for the safety of hydrogen systems

with a specific attention on the following sections :

- 6.6 Factors involved in Hydrogen embrittlement hazards
- Annex C Material data
- 7.2.3 Considerations for vessel and components
- 7.2.4 Prevention of overpressure
- 7.2.5 Piping and connections H₂
- 7.2.7 Components considerations
- 7.3 prevention and mitigation of fire and explosion hazards and risks
- 7.4 Detection considerations
- 7.5.6 Disposal of hydrogen
- 7.5.7 Buildings
- 7.5.8 Ventilation
- 7.5.9 Electrical components
- 7.5.11 Fire protection and fire fighting
- 7.6.5 Storage and transfer operation
- Annex D hydrogen storing compounds

ISO 16528-1:2007 Boilers and pressure vessels -- Part 1: Performance requirements

ISO 22734 - 1 2008 – Hydrogen generators using water electrolysis process part 1 : industrial and commercial applications.

On the aspects related to balance of plants with a specific attention on the following sections :

- 5.4.2.1 Hydrogen storage cylinders

- 5.4.5 Piping, fitting and joints
- 5.4.8 Pressure regulators

ISO 14687 - Hydrogen fuel quality -- Product specification : the storage shall deliver hydrogen with a quality compatible with a fuel cell use according to the standard ISO 14687.

For the transport operations, along with *ISO 16111*, the following standard should be considered:

ISO 19027:2016 Design principles for communication support board using pictorial symbols

3. Preliminary Risk Analysis

The Preliminary Risk Analysis (PRA) allows establishing a first list of possible deviations for each process equipment. Only the deviations that may produce a non-negligible risk are considered.

Taking into account the very early stage of the project and accordingly to the current level of information, this work and the recommendation associated shall not be considered as exhaustive and will be deeply complemented during task 7.1. Nevertheless this very preliminary risk analysis allow to anticipate as much as possible the different safety issues that could possibly happen during the utilization of the developed system and to list the possible barrier that could be considered for the design.

Two sessions of preliminary risk analysis were performed within ENGIE team and with partners in order to have a shared and broad view of potential risks :

27/03/19 with: NOUVELOT Quentin (ENGIE), LALET Eric (ENGIE), MAKHLOUFI Camel (ENGIE), OLIVIER Pierre (ENGIE), KEZIBRI Nouaamane (ENGIE), QUESNEL Sébastien (ENGIE)

29/03/19 with: NOUVELOT Quentin (ENGIE), MAKHLOUFI Camel (ENGIE), OLIVIER Pierre (ENGIE), KEZIBRI Nouaamane (ENGIE), QUESNEL Sébastien (ENGIE), Paola Rizzi (UNITO), Carlo Luetto (TD), Villayat Abbas (TD), Matteo Testi (FBK), Luigi Crema (FBK), Giovanni Capurso (HZG), Jose Bellosta von Colbe (HZG), Holger Stühff (STH)

The following tables resume the discussion of the sessions.

DEVIATIONS	CAUSES	DANGEROUS SITUATIONS		POSSIBLE BARRIERS	
		Occurrence of feared event	Phenomenon	Technical	Organizational
HYDRIDES STORAGE (25 bar g – 50 kgs – configuration and hydride to be confirmed)					
Presence of oxygen in the storage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Electrolyzer failure 	<p>Mix of hydrides/O2 in the storage (the hydride oxidation is an exothermic reaction)</p> <p>Explosive mix of H2/O2 in the storage</p> <p>Increasing the temperature (Mix of hydrides/O2 in the storage and the pressure (desorption of H2 and increase of temperature)</p>	Explosion of storage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Safety barriers on the electrolyzer • High pressure and temperature alarms • Temperature Switch High High with automatic blanketing of the storage • High High Pressure Switch with automatic blanketing of the storage 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Operating procedures for the electrolyzer • Training of technicians

<p>Presence of air in the storage</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Operating error during the start up (no previous blanketing) • Vacuum • Leak/rupture of piping (after the total inventory release) 	<p>Mix of hydrides/air in the storage (the hydride oxidation is an exothermic reaction)</p> <p>Explosive mix of H2/air in the storage</p>	<p>Explosion of the storage</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Safety barriers on the electrolyzer • High pressure and temperature alarms • Temperature Switch High High with automatic blanketing of the storage • High High Pressure Switch with automatic blanketing of the storage 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Operating procedures for the electrolyzer • Training of technicians
<p>DEVIATIONS</p>	<p>CAUSES</p>	<p>DANGEROUS SITUATIONS</p>		<p>POSSIBLE BARRIERS</p>	
		<p>Occurrence of feared event</p>	<p>Phenomenon</p>	<p>Technical</p>	<p>Organizational</p>
<p>Presence of water in the storage</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Electrolyzer failure • Leak in the storage (heat transfer water loop) 	<p>Mix of hydrides/water in the storage (the hydride oxidation is an exothermic reaction)</p> <p>Vaporization of water and formation of H2</p> <p>Increase of the hydrides size leading to a mechanical constraint</p>	<p>Explosion of the storage</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Safety barriers on the electrolyzer • Low Low Flow Switch on the water loop generating blanketing and safe position of the plant • High temperature alarms • Temperature Switch High High with automatic blanketing of the storage 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Operating procedures for the electrolyzer • Training of technicians • Adequation of the materials with the fluids and operating conditions

<p>Presence of electrolyte in the storage (alkaline electrolyzer)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Electrolyzer failure 	<p>Mix hydrides/KOH in the storage (oxidation reaction confirmed with the supplier) Vaporization of KOH and formation of hydrogen (confirmed with the supplier) Increase of the internal volume of hydrides</p>	<p>Explosion of the storage</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Safety barriers on the electrolyzer • High temperature alarms • Temperature Switch High High with automatic blanketing of the storage 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Operating procedures • Training of technicians • Adequation of the materials with the fluids and operating conditions
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DEVIATIONS	CAUSES	DANGEROUS SITUATIONS		POSSIBLE BARRIERS	
		Occurrence of feared event	Phenomenon	Technical	Organizational
<p>Pressure increase</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Electrolyzer failure • External fire closed to the storage • Closing an downstream valve (manual or automatic) • Failure of expansion valve during the desorption phase 	<p>Catastrophic rupture of the storage Rupture of connection H₂ inlet/outlet</p>	<p>Pyrophoric dust release</p> <p>Jet fire</p> <p>FF/VCE</p> <p>Potential health effect (inhalation...)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Safety barriers on the electrolyzer • Rupture disk and Pressure Relief Valve (configuration to be discussed) with a vent on the roof (safe area)High Alarm pressure • High High Pressure Switch with depressurization/safety position and cooling with water loop • High alarm and high high switch temperature • Low Flow Alarm (at the outlet of the storage) • Hydrogen detection with alarm • Ventilation of the container 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Operating procedures • Training of technicians • Preventive Maintenance for the automatic valves • Fire fighting system
<p>Vacuum</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Failure of the heating during the desorption sequence (to be further studied) • Isolation of the storage tank at low pressure high temperature followed by cooling (to be further studied) 	<p>Mix H₂/air in the storage Deformation of the storage and accelerated degradation</p>	<p>Internal explosion</p> <p>Rupture of the storage</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Storage designed for vacuum (to be discussed during the design phase) • Low Pressure Alarm • Low Low Pressure Switch generating the injection of inert gas in the storage • Low Temperature Alarm 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Operating procedures •

DEVIATIONS	CAUSES	DANGEROUS SITUATIONS		POSSIBLE BARRIERS	
		Occurrence of feared event	Phenomenon	Technical	Organizational
Temperature increase	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> External temperature (summer T > 35°C) External fire Pressure increase Failure of the cooling system of the container 	<p>Catastrophic rupture of the storage Dilatation/deformation; Hydrogen leak</p>	<p>Explosion of the storage Jet fire FF/VCE Pyrophoric dust release Potential health effect (inhalation...)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Switch and Alarm temperatures instrumentation The container operating outside must resist to the seasonal conditions (sun) Alarm in case of failure of the cooling system of the container and safe position strategy of the installations Detection of H2 with alarm and ventilation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Operating procedures

<p>Temperature decrease</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • External temperature (winter T < 0°C) • Failure of the container heating system • Uncontrolled drop of the pressure during the desorption sequence 	<p>Vacuum in the storage Freezing of the water loop Potential impact on the PCM to be confirmed by the supplier Potential impact on the hydride material (No impact foreseen at this stage, to be confirmed with the supplier). Impact on the mechanical resistance of the equipments</p>	<p>Internal explosion</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Designed for vacuum (to be discussed during the design phase) • Low Pressure Alarm • Low Low Pressure Switch generating the injection of inert gas in the storage • Low Temperature Alarm • Alarm in case of failure of the heating system of the container and safe position strategy of the installations 	
<p>DEVIATIONS</p>	<p>CAUSES</p>	<p>DANGEROUS SITUATIONS</p>		<p>POSSIBLE BARRIERS</p>	
		<p>Occurrence of feared event</p>	<p>Phenomenon</p>	<p>Technical</p>	<p>Organizational</p>
<p>Internal volume of hydrides increasing</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase of the volume of the hydrides after the cycles 	<p>Dilatation/deformation; Leak of hydrogen</p>	<p>Jet fire FF/VC Pyrophoric dust release Potential health effect (inhalation...)E</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Detection of h2 with alarm • Ventilation system of the container 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Periodic visual Inspection (external) • Design must include the expansion phenomenon for high volumes and vertical configuration
<p>Backflow</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vacuum in the storage 	<p>Hydrogen from the fuel cell going back to the storage</p>	<p>-</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Check valve 	

<p>External aggression</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collision with a vehicle 	<p>Rupture of a inlet/outlet line of H₂; Leak of hydrogen</p>	<p>Jet fire FF/VCE</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Equipments in a container • Detection of h2 with alarm • Ventilation system of the container 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limitation of the circulation in the area
<p>Alteration of the material</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • H2 Mechanical Hydrogen Embrittlement on the storage • Corrosion by water/O2/electrolyte 	<p>Loss of thickness on the storage shell; Leak of H₂</p>	<p>Jet fire FF/VCE Pyrophoric dust release Potential health effect (inhalation...)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Detection of H2 with alarm • Ventilation system of the container 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Material of the piping/storage adapted to the H2 handling (design) • Maintenance /periodic inspection
<p>Failure of electricity</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General or local failure 	<p>Shutdown of the heating/cooling system Shutdown of the ventilation system could lead to accumulation Closing/opening valves with potential overpressure (deviation increase of pressure) and leak of H2</p>	<p>Jet fire FF/VCE Pyrophoric dust release Potential health effect (inhalation...)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Detection of h2 with alarm • Alarm in case of failure of the heating / cooling system of the container and safe position strategy of the installations • Safety position of the valves to be included in the design • Normally closed pneumatic valves • Detection of H2 • Ventilation system of the container 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emergency procedure in case of utilities failure

DEVIATIONS	CAUSES	DANGEROUS SITUATIONS		POSSIBLE BARRIERS	
		Occurrence of feared event	Phenomenon	Technical	Organizational
Failure of nitrogen	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Leak or failure of one nitrogen equipment 	Loss of blanketing (in case of emergency) Potential vacuum conditions in the storage (deviation vacuum)	Internal explosion Rupture of the storage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Low Alarm Pressure in case of failure of the nitrogen 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Emergency procedure in case of utilities failure
Release of hydrides to the atmosphere	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Error during the unloading /loading of hydrides Venting (start up, shutdown, emergency strategy) Leak/rupture of equipment Storage explosion 	Fire / Dust explosion (to be confirmed by the supplier) Toxicity (non toxicity to be confirmed by the supplier)	Pyrophoric dust release Pressure and thermal effects Potential health effect (inhalation...)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Venting with filter (adapted to the flow) Depressurization system with venting and filter (to be studied during the design) Non toxic components required in the hydrides 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Unloading and loading procedure for the hydrides (to be written by the supplier) Start up, shutdown, emergency strategy procedures Training of technicians EPI
Explosion of hydride dust in the storage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduction of the hydrides size leading to dust explosivity of the hydrides 	Dust explosion (to be confirmed by the supplier)	Explosion of the storage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Properties of hydrides to be confirmed by the supplier 	
Presence of hydrogen in the water loop	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Leak on the water loop system To be confirmed by the supplier (depending of the pressure in the storage H2 side versus water side) 	Increase of pressure in the water loop	To be further investigated	To be further investigated	To be further investigated

DEVIATIONS	CAUSES	DANGEROUS SITUATIONS		POSSIBLE BARRIERS	
		Occurrence of feared event	Phenomenon	Technical	Organizational
Buffer (25 bar g – volume to be confirmed)					
Presence of oxygen in the buffer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Electrolyzer failure 	Explosive mix of H2/O2 in the buffer	Explosion of the buffer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Safety barriers on the electrolyzer 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Operating procedures for the electrolyzer • Training of technicians
Presence of air in the buffer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Operating error during the start up (no previous blanketing) • Vacuum • Leak/rupture of piping (after the total inventory release) 	Explosive mix of H2/air in the storage	Explosion of the buffer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Safety barriers on the electrolyzer • Low Alarm Pressure • O2/N2 sensor with alarm 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Operating procedures for the electrolyzer • Training of technicians

DEVIATIONS	CAUSES	DANGEROUS SITUATION		POSSIBLE BARRIERS	
		Occurrence of feared event	Phenomenon	Technical	Organizational
Pressure increase	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Electrolyzer failure • External fire closed to the buffer • Closing an downstream valve (manual or automatic) • Failure of expansion valve during the desorption phase 	<p>Catastrophic rupture of the buffer Rupture of connection H₂ inlet/outlet</p>	<p>Explosion of the buffer Jet fire FF/VCE</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Safety barriers on the electrolyzer • Pressure Relief Valve with venting on the roof (safe area) • High Alarm pressure • Hydrogen detection with alarm • Ventilation system of the container 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Operating procedures • Training of technicians • Preventive Maintenance for the automatic valves • Fire fighting system
Temperature increase	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • External temperature (summer T > 35°C) • External fire • Pressure increase 	<p>Catastrophic rupture of the buffer Dilatation/deformation; Hydrogen leak</p>	<p>Explosion of the buffer Jet fire FF/VCE</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The container operating outside must resist to the seasonal conditions (sun) • Alarm in case of failure of the cooling system of the container and safe position strategy of the installations • Detection of H₂ with alarm • Ventilation system of the container 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Operating procedures

DEVIATIONS	CAUSES	DANGEROUS SITUATION		POSSIBLE BARRIERS	
		Occurrence of feared event	Phenomenon	Technical	Organizational
Vacuum	Vacuum on the hydride storage system	Mix H₂/air in the buffer Deformation of the buffer and accelerated degradation	Internal explosion Rupture of the buffer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low Pressure Alarm • Low Low Pressure Switch generating the injection of inert gas in the storage • Buffer designed for vacuum (to be discussed during the design phase) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Operating procedures
Temperature decrease	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • External temperature (winter T < 0°C) • Failure of the container heating system • Uncontrolled drop of the pressure during the desorption sequence 	Impact on the resistance of the equipments Hydrogen leak	Jet fire FF/VCE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alarm in case of failure of the heating system of the container and safe position strategy of the installations • Detection of h₂ with alarm • Ventilation system of the container 	
External aggression	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collision with a vehicle 	Rupture of a inlet/outlet line of H ₂ ; Leak of hydrogen	Jet fire FF/VCE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Equipment in a container • Detection of h₂ with alarm 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limitation of the circulation in the area
Alteration of the material	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • H₂ Mechanical Hydrogen Embrittlement on the buffer • Corrosion by water/O₂/electrolyte 	Loss of thickness on the buffer shell; Leak of H₂	Jet fire FF/VCE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Detection of H₂ with alarm • Ventilation system of the container 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Material of the piping/storage adapted to the H₂ handling (design) • Maintenance /periodic inspection

DEVIATIONS	CAUSES	DANGEROUS SITUATION		POSSIBLE BARRIERS	
		Occurrence of feared event	Phenomenon	Technical	Organizational
PCM (pression – temperature - volume to be confirmed)					
Presence of PCM in the storage	To be further investigated when design will be more advanced				
Presence of water/O2/KOH/N2/H2/Air In the PCM system	To be further investigated when design will be more advanced				
Other risks	To be further investigated when design will be more advanced				

4. Safety Recommendations

In addition of the applicable regulations and standards (section 2), and according to the best practices, the Preliminary Risk Assessment recommend to follow the following requirements :

- The storage system must be protected from overpressure and excess of temperature with alarms (High/Low) and switch (Pressure Relief Valve, Pressure Switch High High/Low Low & Temperature Switch High High with an action of blanketing the storage and safety configuration of the system for each case)
- The Pressure Relief Valve must be connected to a vent releasing in a safe place outside of the container (with a Rupture disk and an appropriate filter)
All the gas vented from the system shall be filtered with an appropriate filter insuring that no hydrid material is released in the atmosphere. This filtered must be designed taking into account the high flow of gas during possible safety venting of the total storage system.
- More generally the risk of hydride atmospheric release must be prevented for the whole life cycle of the storage system (transport, commissioning, operation, maintenance, hydride material replacement, decommissioning and end of life...). Appropriate shaping of the hydride is a solution that allow to reduce possible presence of fine particulate and should also be considered as a trade off with performance.
- The storage must be protected against vacuum (possible protection include Pressure Switch Low Low blanketing the storage, vacuum design pressure)
- The system will be equipped with a depressurisation system in case of emergency with a release to a vent system in a safe area.
- The outlet of hydrogen from the storage must be provided with a filter in order to prevent the circulation of hydride dust through the Fuel Cell
- Redact and provide procedures to fill out and fill in the PCM fluid and the hydrides of the storage including the safety measures in order to realise these operations in safe conditions.
- The PCM must be a non toxic fluid and had to be compatible with the hydride and hydrogen. (provide a MSDS)
- The hydride material chosen must be a non toxic component (provide a MSDS)
- The enclosure container must be provided with a ventilation system and a detection of hydrogen in order to prevent and detect the accumulation of hydrogen inside.
- The heating/cooling system of the container will generate an alarm in case of failure
- The failure of blanketing system and cooling water system must be detected and an alarm associated will inform the operators of the failure.
- The system must be provided with an automatic shut off valve at the outlet of hydrogen in order to stop a leak.
- For hydrogen piping, welded connection must be preferred in order to reduce the probability of hydrogen leak and the connections will be test before the start-up in order to prevent any leak of hydrogen..
- More generally all the life cycle of the storage system shall be taken into account regarding easy and safe handling (transport, commissioning, operation, maintenance, spare part replacement, consumable replacement, hydride material and PCM replacement, decommissioning and end of life...)

5. Conclusions

In the deliverable, the main parameters planned for the integrated system have been described. In addition, a preliminary PRA has been assessed.